

Evaluation of PR Expression and It's Comparison with Pathologic Parameters in Breast Cancer Patients Presenting to A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital in Eastern India

Debanjan Bhattacharjee¹, Himel Bera², Karabi Konar³, Nazir Abdul Wasim⁴, Suman Sardar⁵, Prasenjit Sadhukhan⁶

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Midnapore Medical College & Hospital, Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal 721101, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay Government Medical College & Hospital, PO- Uluberia, Howrah, West Bengal 711315, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Malda Medical College & Hospital, Malda, West Bengal 732101, India

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay Government Medical College & Hospital, PO- Uluberia, Howrah, West Bengal 711315, India

⁵Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay Government Medical College & Hospital, PO- Uluberia, Howrah, West Bengal 711315, India

⁶RMO, Department of Paediatrics, Midnapore Medical College & Hospital, Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal 721101, India

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Nazir Abdul Wasim

Conflict of Interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The prognosis of breast cancer depends on the histological type, size of the tumor, tumor necrosis, skin, nipple and chest wall invasion, lymphovascular invasion, grade, stage, the status of estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2), cell proliferation marker (ki-67), and type of therapy. Estrogen receptor and progesterone receptor expression in breast cancer is, so far, the most useful predictive marker. Hormone receptor expression has been reported to be low in breast cancer patients from developing countries including India. The pattern of progesterone receptor expression in cancer breast subjects from rural areas is not well studied.

Materials and Methods: Immunohistochemistry was used for evaluation of PR expression in the mastectomy specimens. Tumour size from the mastectomy specimen was recorded; number of lymph nodes was noted. Tissue processing and staining with haematoxylin & eosin was to be done. Post mastectomy grading of the malignant breast lesion was done according to Scarff-Bloom- Richardson's grading (SBR) system in haematoxylin & eosin stained slides.

Results: Among the histopathological types of the tumours, IDC NOS constituted 40 cases (86.9%), Invasive lobular carcinoma constituted 2 cases (4.3%), medullary carcinoma 2 cases (4.3%), invasive papillary carcinoma and mucinous carcinoma 1 case each (2.2%). The total no of ER positive and negative cases were 21(45.7%) and 25(54.7%) respectively. The total no of PR positive cases was 18(39.1%) and that of negative cases was 28(60.9%). This indicates majority of the tumours did not have hormonal receptor expression.

Conclusion: A significant inverse association between ER and PR expression and higher tumour grades and axillary lymph node metastases was seen. No significant association was found between ER & PR expression and the rest of the clinicopathological parameters.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Estrogen Receptor, Progesterone Receptor, Histological Subtypes, PR Expression, Eastern India.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Breast cancer is the most common cancer in women worldwide. In 2022, there were 2.3 million women diagnosed with breast cancer and 670 000 deaths globally. Breast cancer occurs in every country of the world in women at any age after

puberty but with increasing rates in later life [1]. Epidemiological studies have shown that the global burden of BC is expected to cross almost 2 million by the year 2030. In India, the incidence has increased significantly, almost by 50%, between

1965 and 1985 [2]. In the majority of breast cancer patients, estrogen receptor (ER) and/or progesterone receptor (PR) are overexpressed and promote the development of breast cancer [3, 4]. The major prognostic factors for breast carcinoma include histological type, grading, axillary lymph node status, lymphatic and vascular invasion, hormone receptor status and surface epithelial growth-factor receptors. Still others are DNA ploidy, human epidermal growth factor-2 (HER-2) oncogene, cathepsin-D, angiogenesis and mutant p53 expression. However, none of these is shown to have an independent significance as a single prognostic marker [5].

The prognostic and therapeutic implications of estrogen receptor (ER) and progesterone receptor (PR) in breast cancer have been studied extensively. Up to 75% of primary breast carcinomas express ER, about 50% co-express PR and about 20% have no ER or PR expression [6]. Hormone receptor determination acts primarily as a predictive factor for response to therapeutic and adjuvant hormonal therapy.[7] The presence of ER is related to a favorable response to tamoxifen therapy and improved overall survival.

Although analysis of progesterone receptor (PR) expression is generally reported along with ER expression, and IHC determination of PR expression has now been clinically validated [8]. It has further been conclusively demonstrated that PR status is independently associated with disease-free and overall survival, that is, patients with ER-positive/PR-positive tumours have a better prognosis than patients with ER-positive/PR-negative tumours, who in turn have a better prognosis than patients with ER-negative/ PR-negative tumours [9]. The concluding fact remains that Breast cancer patients with tumours that are ER positive and/or PR positive have lower mortality risk after diagnosis in comparison to women with ER negative and/or PR negative disease [10]. The survival advantage for women with hormone receptor-positive tumours is intensified by treatment with neo-adjuvant hormonal and/ or chemotherapeutic regimens [11], which have been stated by various clinical trials.

Our aims in this study are to evaluate the expression of ER and PR and the overexpression of Her-2/neu in patients with breast cancer in rural West Bengal, and to study the expression of these with other prognostic parameters for cancer breasts, such as histological type, histological grade, tumor size, patients' age and number of lymph node metastases.

Materials and Methods

An institution based cross sectional observational study was done at Burdwan Medical College & Hospital among patients' adult females having

history of breast lump with or without enlarged lymph nodes from rural area around Burdwan. All the patients suspected of breast malignancy were clinically evaluated with age >25 years (as breast cancer is common beyond this age) and were included in the study. All the mastectomy specimens sent to Department of Pathology for histopathological examination were considered in the study. The study was conducted after receiving approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee, Burdwan Medical College & Hospital, West Bengal.

Parameters Studied: Immunohistochemistry was used for evaluation of HER-2/neu expression in the mastectomy specimens. Tumour size from the mastectomy specimen was recorded; number of lymph nodes was noted. Tissue processing and staining with haematoxylin & eosin was to be done. Post mastectomy grading of the malignant breast lesion was done according to Scarff-Bloom- Richardson's grading (SBR) system in haematoxylin & eosin stained slides [12]. Detailed clinical examination of the breast and the lump was done and presence of any axillary or cervical lymph nodes was also noted.

In H&E stained histopathological sections following parameters were studied in case of primary tumour: Histological type, microscopic grading (Nottingham's Modification of Bloom's Richardson's grading system [13]; degree of differentiation and stromal characteristics.

In case of lymph nodes: Number of the lymph nodes showing invasion by tumour and pattern of lymph node reaction is noted whether it is follicular hyperplasia or sinus histiocytosis. Protocol for Immunohistochemistry for Polymer Detection System (Novocastra) (used in HER-2/neu and ER and PR) was used. Immunostaining of the HER-2 protein is to be performed for all specimens. A semi quantitative score was used to record results of Estrogen receptor & Progesterone receptor staining.

Data entry was done right after capturing of relevant data for a given subject is complete. Logistic regression, Discriminant function and Multivariate analysis by SPSS software for Windows' was used for data-analysis.

Results

Forty six (46) formalin fixed and paraffin embedded surgical specimens of different malignant lesions of breast were studied based on histopathological and immunohistochemical findings.

Age distribution and histopathological types of tumours: The number of invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC NOS) cases were 40 (85.9%), 7 cases (17.5%) of which were between 30-39 years, 18 cases (45%) were between 40-49 years, 11 cases

(27.5%) were between 50-59 years and 4 (10%) cases were obtained at 60 years or above [Table 1].

Table 1: Age distribution and histopathological types of tumours

Age (Years)	No of IDC cases	Percentage
30-39	7	17.5
40-49	18	45
50-59	11	27.5
60 and above	4	10
Invasive Lobular Carcinoma		
30-39	0	0
40-49	1	50
50-59	0	0
60 and above	1	50
Medullary Carcinoma		
30-39	0	0
40-49	2	100
50-59	0	0
60 and above	0	0
Invasive Papillary Carcinoma		
30-39	0	0
40-49	0	0
50-59	1	100
60 and above	0	0
Mucinous Carcinoma		
30-39	0	0
40-49	1	100
50-59	0	0
60 and above	0	0

Invasive lobular carcinomas were observed on 2 occasions (4.3%); 1 case was between 40-49 years of age and the other was above 60 years of age. The number of medullary carcinoma cases were 2 (4.3%), both of which were seen in the age ranging between 40-49 years. Only 1(2.2%) case of invasive papillary carcinoma was found in the age ranging between 50-59 years [Table 3].

Age distribution and histopathological grades of the tumours: Grading of 42 cases was done and

only 1 case (2.4%) of Grade I was seen; whereas 25 cases (59.5%) belonged to Grade II, and 16 cases (38.1%) to Grade III. The Grade I case was observed in the age range of 40-49 years of age.

Out of 25 cases of Grade II, 4 cases (9.5%) were between 30-39 years of age, 11 cases (26.2%) were between 40-49 years, 8 cases (19.1%) were between 50-59 years, and 2 cases (4.8%) were found at 60 years or above (Table 2).

Table 2: Age distribution and histopathological grades of the tumours (n= 42)

Age (Years)	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III
30-39	0	4(9.5%)	3(7.1%)
40-49	1(2.4%)	11(26.2%)	7(16.7%)
50-59	0	8(19.1%)	4(9.5%)
60 and above	0	2(4.8%)	2(4.8%)

Histopathological types of tumours seen: Among the histopathological types of the tumours, IDC NOS constituted 40 cases (86.9%), Invasive lobular carcinoma constituted 2 cases (4.3%), medullary carcinoma 2 cases (4.3%), and invasive papillary carcinoma and mucinous carcinoma 1 case each (2.2%) (Table 3/ Fig. 1-3).

Table 3: Histopathological types of tumours

Histopathological Type	No	Percentage
IDC	40	86.9
Invasive Lobular Carcinoma	2	4.3
Medullary Carcinoma	2	4.3
Invasive Papillary Carcinoma	1	2.2
Mucinous Carcinoma	1	2.2
Total	46	100

Age and PR expression: The total no. of PR positive cases was 18 (39.1%) and that of negative cases was 28 (60.9%).

Out of the 18 positive cases, 5 cases (10.9%) were found in the age range of 30-39 years, 7 cases (15.2%) in the age range of 40-49 years, 6 cases (13%) in the age range 50-59 years, and there was

no case above 60 years. Out of the 28 negative cases, 2 cases (4.3%) were found in the age range of 30-39 years, 15 cases (32.6%) in the age range of 40-49 years, 6 cases (13%) in the age range 50-59 years, and there were 5 cases (10.9%) above 60 years. The value of χ^2 for PR expression in different age groups was 0.17 (at 1 df) and hence no significant association ($p > 0.05$) was found [Table 4].

Table 4: Age, tumour size and PR expression

Age Groups	PR Expression			
	PR Positive		PR Negative	
	Cases	%	Cases	%
30-39	5	10.9%	2	4.3%
40-49	7	15.2%	15	32.6%
50-59	6	13%	6	13%
≥ 60	0	0	5	10.9%
Total	18	39.1%	28	60.9%
Tumour Size	Cases	%	Cases	%
T1	2	4.3%	0	0
T2	3	6.5%	7	15.2%
T3	1	2.2%	4	8.7%
T4	12	26.1%	17	36.9%

Out of the 18 positive PR cases, T1 constituted 2 cases (4.3%), T2 constituted 3 cases (6.5%), T3 -1 cases (2.2%), T4 -12 cases (26.1%).

Out of the 28 negative PR cases, there was no case for T1, T2 constituted 7 cases (15.2%), T3 -4 cases (8.7%), T4 -17 cases (36.9%). The value of χ^2 for PR expression in different tumour sizes was 0.04 (at 1 df) and hence no significant association ($p > 0.05$) was found [Table 4].

PR expression and Histopathological types: Out of the 18 positive PR cases, 17 cases (36.9%) were positive for IDC NOS, 1 case (2.2%) for invasive lobular carcinoma and papillary carcinoma. Out of the 28 negative PR cases, 23 cases (50%) were negative for IDC NOS, 1 case (2.2%) each for invasive lobular carcinoma and mucinous carcinoma and 2 cases (4.3%) for medullary carcinoma [Table 5].

Table 5: Histopathology types and PR expression

HP Types	PR Expression			
	PR Positive		PR Negative	
IDC	17	36.9%	23	50%
Invasive Lobular Carcinoma	1	2.2%	1	2.2%
Papillary Carcinoma	0	0	0	0%
Mucinous Carcinoma	0	0	1	2.2%
Medullary Carcinoma	0	0	2	4.3%
Total	18		28	

PR expression and Histopathological grades of tumours: Grading of 42 cases was done. About 17 cases (40.5%) were positive for PR and 25 cases (59.5%) were negative for PR expression. Out of the 17 positive PR cases, Grade II constituted 15 cases (35.7%), and Grade III -2 cases (4.8%). Out of the 25 negative PR cases, Grade I constituted 1 case (2.4%), Grade II -10 cases (23.8%), and Grade III -14 cases (33.3%).

The value of χ^2 for PR expression in different tumour sizes was 6.63 (at 1 df) and hence significant association ($p < 0.01$) was found between tumour Grades and PR expression. This implies PR positivity decreases with higher grades of tumours [Table 6/ Fig. 4-5].

Table 6: PR expression and grading of tumour

Grade	PR Expression			
	PR Positive (n=17)		PR Negative (n=25)	
	Cases	%	Cases	%
I	0	0	1	2.4%
II	15	35.7%	10	23.8%
III	2	4.8%	14	33.3%

PR expression and lymph node metastases: Out of the 18 PR positive cases, 7 cases (15.2%) had lymph node metastases and 11 cases (23.9%) had no lymph node metastases. Out of the 28 PR negative cases, 24 cases (52.2%) had lymph node metastases and 4 cases (8.7%) had no lymph node metastases.

The value of χ^2 for ER expression and lymph node metastases was 8.9 (at 1 df) and hence significant association ($p < 0.01$) was found between lymph node metastases and PR expression. This implies PR negative cases had more lymph node metastases [Table 7].

Table 7: PR expression and lymph node metastases

Lymph node metastases	PR Expression			
	PR Positive		PR Negative	
	Cases	%	Cases	%
+Ve	7	15.2%	24	52.2%
-Ve	11	23.9%	04	8.7%
Total	18	39.1%	28	60.9%

PR expression and skin involvement: Out of the 18 PR positive cases, 10 cases (21.7%) had skin involved and 8 cases (17.4%) did not show any skin involvement. Out of the 28 PR negative cases, 18 cases (39.1%) had skin involved and 10 cases

(21.7%) did not show any skin involvement. The value of χ^2 for PR expression and skin involvement was 0.35 (at 1 df) and hence no significant association ($p > 0.05$) was found between skin involvement and PR expression [Table 8].

Table 8: PR expression and skin involvement

Skin Involvement	PR Expression			
	PR Positive		PR Negative	
	Cases	%	Cases	%
+ve	10	21.7%	18	39.1%
-ve	08	17.4%	10	21.7%
Total	18	39.1%	28	60.9%

Clinical staging and PR expression: Out of the 18 positive PR cases, Stage IIA constituted 4 cases (8.7%), Stage IIB 2 cases (4.3%), and Stage IIIB 12 cases (26.1%). Out of the 28 negative PR cases, Stage IIA constituted 4 cases (8.7%), Stage IIB 1 case (2.2%), Stage IIIA 6 cases (13%), and Stage IIIB 17 cases (36.9%) [Table 9].

Table 9: Clinical staging and PR expression

Staging	PR Expression				
	Staging	PR Positive		PR Negative	
		Cases	%	Cases	%
I	0	0	0	0	
IIA	04	8.7%	04	8.7%	
IIB	02	4.3%	01	2.2%	
IIIA	0	0	06	13%	
IIIB	12	26.1%	17	36.9%	
IV	0	0	0	0	
Total	18	39.1%	28	60.1%	

Figure 1: Microscopy picture illustrating the in situ component (H&E 100X)

Figure 2: Microscopy picture illustrating the DC grade III with lympho vascular invasion (100x, H&E)

Figure 3: Microscopy picture illustrating the metastatic deposit of Invasive ductal carcinoma in lymph node (H&E100 X)

Figure 4: Microscopy picture illustrating the patterns of PR positive invasive papillary carcinoma (100X)

Figure 5: Microscopy picture illustrating the patterns of PR negative invasive papillary carcinoma (100X)

Discussion

Among the hormone receptors, it can be said that expression of ER in breast tumour might indicate the hormonal dependence and will regress with appropriate endocrine manipulation and assessment of PR should assist in predicting response to hormonal therapy more accurately [14]. In the present study, 46 formalin fixed and paraffin embedded surgical specimens of invasive breast carcinoma were evaluated for ER, PR expression and HER-2/neu protein overexpression by applying immunohistochemical stain using antibody for ER, PR and HER-2/neu and were compared with clinicopathological parameters like age, tumour size, histopathological grades, lymph node metastases, skin involvement and surgical staging. Out of the 46 cases, maximum patients were in the age group of

40-49 years (47.8%), followed by 26.1% from 50-59 years, 15.2% from 30-39 years of age and 10.9% above 60 years. This is in accordance with the study conducted by Hussian M A et al (1994), who found the peak incidence between age range 41-50 years [15]. Poonam Panjwani et al (2010) [16] also found most of the cases below 50 years. M.I.Perez et al also found most of the cases between 40-49 years (27.8%) [17].

Grading of 42 cases was done and 2.4% of the cases belonged to Grade I, whereas 59.5% of the cases belonged to Grade II, and Grade III constituted 38.1% and therefore majority of the cases belonged to Grade II. Similar findings were noted by Zubair Ahmad et al, .2009 who found 4.17% Grade I cases, 75.83% Grade II cases, and 20% Grade III cases [18]. Our findings also closely matched with the

study of Le Doussal et al, 1989 [19]. In his study, 11-14% cases were Grade I, 55-57% cases were Grade II, and 29-34% cases were Grade III. Lymph node metastases were seen in 31 cases (67.4%), and it was absent in 15 cases (32.6%). Our study closely matched the study conducted by Esraa Abdul-Aal Salman Al-Dujaily, 2008 [20], who found lymph node metastases were positive in 69.4% cases and negative in 30.6% cases. Aziz et al., (2001) [21] observed positive axillary lymph node status in (54%), while negative axillary lymph node status in (46%). Al Rashed et al., (2007) [22] also reported 66% positive lymph node involvement and negative lymph node were observed in 34% cases. All these studies are consistent with that of the present study.

In the present study, 76% of the cases belonged to Stage III while 24% to Stage II. This is in accordance to the study conducted by Esraa Abdul-Aal Salman Al-Dujaily, 2008 [20], who found 56.9% were of stage III and stage II constituted 31.9% of the cases. This frequency agrees with Aziz et al., (2001) [21] who reported in their study 40.63% of stage III and 36.2% of stage II cases.

Out of the 18 positive PR cases, 5 cases (10.9%) were found in the age range of 30-39 years, 7 cases (15.2%) in the age range of 40-49 years, 6 cases (13%) in the age range 50-59 years, and there was no case above 60 years. Out of the 28 negative cases, 2 cases (4.3%) were found in the age range of 30-39 years, 15 cases (32.6%) in the age range of 40-49 years, 6 cases (13%) in the age range 50-59 years, and there were 5 cases (10.9%) above 60 years. Hence we could not find any statistically significant association between age distribution and Hormone receptor expression. Our results are consistent with the findings of E. Ur Rahman (2011) [23] who did not find any association between age distribution and hormone receptor expression. But the study conducted by Lucia A et al (2001) [24] showed that hormone receptor expression increased significantly with age.

We also did not find any significant association between tumour size and ER & PR expression. Our findings are supported by the study conducted by E. Ur Rahman (2011) [23] but Lucia A et al (2001) [24] found a significant association between ER, PR expression and tumour size.

Out of the 18 PR positive cases, 17 cases (36.9%) were IDC NOS, 1 case (2.2%) each were invasive lobular carcinoma and papillary carcinoma. Out of the 28 PR negative cases, 23 cases (50%) were IDC NOS, 1 case (2.2%) each were invasive lobular carcinoma and Mucinous carcinoma and 2 cases (4.3%) were Medullary carcinoma. Our findings closely matched with that of Chauhan N in 2010 [25] who found papillary carcinoma, mucinous carcinoma has higher rates of ER & PR positivity

while Medullary carcinoma cases were typically negative for hormone receptor expression. Our findings are also in accordance with that of S.B. Desai et al in 2000 [26] who concluded that invasive lobular, mucinous and mixed tumours are frequently ER & PR positive while invasive ductal and medullary carcinomas were predominantly negative for ER & PR.

Out of the 20 ER positive cases (20 cases were ER positive out of the 42 cases whose grading was done), Grade I constituted 1 case (2.4%), Grade II - 15 cases (35.7%), and Grade III - 4 cases (9.5%). Out of the 22 (22 cases were ER negative out of the 42 cases whose grading was done) ER negative cases, Grade II constituted 10 cases (23.8%), and Grade III - 12 cases (25.6%). Out of the 17 PR positive cases, Grade II constituted 15 cases (35.7%), and Grade III - 2 cases (4.8%). Out of the 25 PR negative cases, Grade I constituted 1 case (2.4%), Grade II - 10 cases (23.8%), and Grade III - 14 cases (33.3%). Hence our study showed a significant inverse association between tumour grades and ER & PR expression. Our findings are in accordance with that of Luua A et al (2001) (299) who observed that lower histopathological grades have statistically more ER & PR expression. Tero A. H. Jarvinen et al (2000) also noted that hormone receptor expression decreases with higher tumour grades [27]. Chandra N, 2010 [25] also found similar results. However, E. Ur Rahman (2011) [23] did not find any statistically significant association between ER & PR expression and histopathological grades. Our study also revealed that ER expression increases with PR expression and vice-versa and we found a significant association between the two. Our observations are keeping in with Almasri et al., (2005) [28], who concluded positive correlation between ER and PR expression. A strong correlation between ER and PR expression was noted in our series. Unlike ER, however, there was only a low tendency for PR to be associated with smaller carcinomas and with older patients, but this tendency was not statistically significant [28].

Singh R et al study (2014) had revealed that the invasive ductal carcinoma was the most common subtype (94%). The ER status was available in 101 (49.3%), PR in 99 (48.0%), and HER2 in 82 (39.8%) cases. In patients in whom this data were available, ER was positive in 44.6%, PR in 40.4%, and HER2 in 34.2%. Out of the 82 patients in whom data on all three receptors were available, 34.1% patients had triple negative tumors. Analysis of their data showed a trend toward increasing ER and PR expression with age but this was not statistically significant. The average age of menopause was between 40-50 years of age [29].

Conclusion

An inverse statistically significant association between lymph node metastases and hormonal receptor positivity was also noticed. This indicates ER & PR positive tumours have less no of lymph node metastases.

No significant association between skin involvement and ER & PR positivity was observed. Regarding clinical staging and ER & PR positivity, no significant association was found. Comparison between ER and PR expression showed a statistically significant association between the two, which means majority of the tumours which were positive for ER, also showed PR positivity and vice-versa.

Ethical Approval: Ethics approval has been taken from IEC, Burdwan Medical College & Hospital, and West Bengal.

References

- Breast cancer. World Health Organization. Available at https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/breast-cancer?gad_source=1&gclid=Cj0KCCQjwlvW2BhDyARIsADnLe-LCnijLKYDk8vqVrb9hSfanksHdoV79xPias2sUQYpbKo-134IGHskaAmd2EALw_wcB [Accessed on 21 June, 2024]
- Mehrotra R, Yadav K. Breast cancer in India: Present scenario and the challenges ahead. *World J Clin Oncol.* 2022 Mar 24; 13(3):209-218. doi: 10.5306/wjco. v13.i3.209. PMID: 35433294; PMCID: PMC8966510.
- Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Dikshit R, Eser S, Mathers C, Rebelo M, et al. Cancer incidence and mortality worldwide: sources, methods and major patterns in GLOBOCAN 2012. *Int J Cancer.* 2015 Mar 1; 136(5):E359-86. doi: 10.1002/ijc.29210. Epub 2014 Oct 9. PMID: 25220842.
- Sleightholm R, Neilsen BK, Elkhatib S, Flores L, Dukkipati S, Zhao R, et al. Percentage of Hormone Receptor Positivity in Breast Cancer Provides Prognostic Value: A Single-Institute Study. *J Clin Med Res.* 2021 Jan; 13(1):9-19. doi: 10.14740/jocmr4398. Epub 2021 Jan 12. PMID: 33613796; PMCID: PMC7869562.
- Handa U, Kumar A, Kundu R, Dalal U, Mohan H. Evaluation of grading and hormone receptor immunostaining on fine needle aspirates in carcinoma breast. *J Cytol.* 2015 Jan-Mar; 32(1):1-5. doi: 10.4103/0970-9371.155222. PMID: 25948935; PMCID: PMC4408669.
- Hanley KZ, Birdsong GG, Cohen C, Siddiqui MT. Immunohistochemical detection of estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor, and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 expression in breast carcinomas: Comparison on cell block, needle-core, and tissue block preparations. *Cancer.* 2009; 117:279–88.
- Railo M, Nordling S, Krogerus L, Sioris T, von Smitten K. Preoperative assessment of proliferative activity and hormonal receptor status in carcinoma of the breast: A comparison of needle aspiration and needle-core biopsies to the surgical specimen. *Diagn Cytopathol.* 1996; 15:205–10.
- Mohsin SK, Weiss H, Havighrurst T, et al. Progesterone receptor by immunohistochemistry and clinical outcome in breast cancer: a validation study. *Mod.Pathol.* 2004; 17:1545-1554.
- Bardou VJ, Arpino G, Elledge RM, et al. Progesterone receptor status significantly improves outcome prediction over estrogen receptor status alone for adjuvant endocrine therapy in two large breast cancer databases. *J Clin Oncol.* 2003; 21:1973-1979.
- Fisher B, Redmond C, Fisher ER, Caplan R. Relative worth of estrogen or progesterone receptor and pathologic characteristics of differentiation as indicators of prognosis in node negative breast cancer patients: findings from National Surgical Adjuvant Breast and Bowel Project Protocol B-06. *J Clin Oncol.* 1988; 6:1076-1087.
- Goldhirsch A, Wood WC, Gelber RD, Coates AS, Thurlimann B, Senn HJ. Meeting highlights: updated international expert consensus on the primary therapy of early breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol.* 2003; 21:3357-3365.
- Bloom HJG, Richardson WW. Histological grading and prognosis in breast cancer. *Br J Cancer* 1957; 11:359–377.
- Nottingham or Bloom-Richardson (BR) Score/Grade. <https://staging.seer.cancer.gov/cs/input/02.05.50/breast/ssf/?version=/tnm/home/1.7/> [Accessed on 11 September 2023]
- Horwitz KB, Koseki Y, McGuire WL. Estrogen control of progesterone receptor in human breast cancer: role of estradiol and antiestrogen. *Endocrinology.* 1978 Nov; 103(5):1742-51. doi: 10.1210/endo-103-5-1742. PMID: 748014.
- Hussain MA, Ali S, Tyagi SP, Reza H. Incidence of cancer breast at Aligarh. *J Indian Med Assoc.* 1994 Sep; 92(9):296-7. PMID: 7814903.
- Panjwani P, Epari S, Karpate A, Shrisat H, Rajshekharan P, Basak R, et al. Assessment of HER-2/neu status in breast cancer using fluorescence in situ hybridization & immunohistochemistry: Experience of a tertiary cancer referral centre in India. *Indian J Med Res* 2010 September; 132: 287-294.
- Perez MI, Picon G, Ugalde J. Her-2/neu in breast cancer patients immunohistochemical comparison with monoclonal and polyclonal antibodies amplification with chromogen in situ hybridization (cish). In Instituto Del Cancer. Solca. Cuenca; Ecuador.

18. Ahmad Z, Khurshid A, Quereshi A, Idress R, Asghar N, Kayani N. Breast carcinoma grading, estimation of tumour size, axillary lymph node status, staging, and nottingham prognostic index scoring on mastectomy specimens. *Indian J Pathol Microbiol* 2009; 52(4):477-81.
19. Kaptain S, Tan LK, Chen B. Her-2/neu and breast cancer. *Diagn Mol Pathol*. 2001 Sep; 10(3):139-52. doi: 10.1097/00019606-200109000-00001. PMID: 11552716.
20. Al-Dujaily ES. Pathological Study of Breast Cancer by Application of Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor Type II (HER-2/neu) (Immunohistochemical study) a thesis. 2008.
21. Aziz SA, Pervez S, Khan S, Kayani N, Azam SI, Rahbar MH. Significance of immunohistochemical c-ErbB-2 product localisation pattern for prognosis in human breast cancer. *Pathol Oncol Res*. 2001; 7(3):190-6. doi: 10.1007/BF03032348. PMID: 11692145.
22. Rashed MM, Ragab MN, Galal KM. The association of HER-2/neu overexpression in relation with p53 nuclear accumulation, hormonal receptor status and common clinicopathological prognostic parameters in a series of Egyptian women with invasive ductal carcinoma. *Eur. J. Gen. Med*. 2007; 4:73-79.
23. Rahman EU, Shaharyar A, Haafeez M, Goraya AW. Relationship of ER, PR, and HER2-neu status with age, menopausal status, and axillary nodal status in early breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*. 2011; 29(suppl abstr e 11011).
24. Lucia A, Eisenberg A, Koifman S, Magalhaes LM, Rezende Cd. Hormone receptors: Association with prognostic factors for breast cancer. *Revista Brasileira de Cancerologia*. 2001; 47(1): 49-58.
25. Chauhan N. Comparative evaluation of HER-2/neu with hormone receptors and other prognostic parameters in carcinoma breast, B.R.D Medical College, D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur. Thesis report for Doctor of Medicine (Pathology). 2011.
26. Desai SB, Moonim MT, Gill AK, Punia RS, Chinoy RF. Hormone receptor status of breast cancer in India: A study of 798 tumours. *The Breast*. 2000; 9(5):267-270.
27. Jarvinen TH, Pelto-Huikko M, Holli K, Isola J. Estrogen Receptor β Is Coexpressed with ER α and PR and Associated with Nodal Status, Grade, and Proliferation Rate in Breast Cancer. *Am J Pathol*. 2000 January; 156(1):29-35.
28. Almasri NM, Al Hamad M. Immunohistochemical evaluation of human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 and estrogen and progesterone receptors in breast carcinoma in Jordan. *Breast Cancer Res*. 2005; 7(5):R598-604. doi: 10.1186/bcr1200. Epub 2005 May 24. PMID: 16168103; PMCID: PMC1242123.
29. Singh R, Gupta S, Pawar SB, Pawar RS, Gandham SV, Prabhudesai S. Evaluation of ER, PR and HER-2 receptor expression in breast cancer patients presenting to a semi urban cancer centre in Western India. *J Cancer Res Ther*. 2014 Jan-Mar; 10(1):26-8. doi: 10.4103/0973-1482.131348. PMID: 24762482.